

Influence of some Thiophene Derivatives on the Corrosion of Iron in Nitric Acid Solution

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Corrosion of iron in 2M HNO₃ has been studied by the electrochemical polarisation and weight-loss measurement. The effect of some thiophene derivatives has been investigated. The results show that the inhibitors under consideration, influence both the cathodic and anodic processes, and are adsorbed on the metal surface in molecular form. They do not change the mechanism of the reaction between iron and nitric acid but decrease its rate. This effect is controlled by the values of their dipole moments. Weight-loss technique also gives the same order of inhibition efficiency of the tested inhibitors.

ONE of the most important considerations in any industry today is the reduction in overall cost in their protection and maintenance. And because iron is the backbone of the industry so the inhibition of iron corrosion in acid solutions of organic inhibitors has been studied in considerable detail. The inhibitory effects of alcohols, amides, amines, anilines, azoles, mercaptans, oximes and thioethers have been studied to mention but a few¹⁻⁹. In nearly all the cases, there was evidence of chemisorption of the inhibitor and it was observed that the inhibitors were of mixed type, that is, both the anodic and cathodic polarisation curves were affected. Carositi *et al.*¹⁰ and Kaminski¹¹ studied the inhibition of iron corrosion in sulphuric acid by nitriles and thiophene derivatives, respectively, and a higher efficiency was observed.

In the present investigation corrosion of iron in 2 M nitric acid was studied. Influence of thiophene, 2-acetylthiophene, 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde and 2-thiophenecarboxylic acid has been studied. The object of this work is to suggest the effective inhibitors towards corrosion of iron by nitric acid.

Experimental

Iron test pieces of 99.99% of purity was used. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solution of 2 M HNO₃ was prepared in distilled water. The specimens of iron (1 × 2 cm) were used for the weight-loss measurements. The preparation, testing and cleaning procedures were the same as reported earlier¹². All the experiments were carried out at 30 ± 1°. Inhibitive efficiencies were calculated from the weight-loss values using the equation,

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{W_B - W_I}{W_B} \times 100$$

where, W_B is the weight-loss in 2 M HNO₃ solution and W_I is that in inhibited solution.

For the galvanostatic measurements electrodes were constructed from analytical reagent grade iron wire (dia 0.053 cm). A 2 cm length of wire was inserted in the small opening of a tube so that about 1 cm extended beyond the end of the tube. The procedures for the potential measurements were adopted as those described by Czatos¹³.

The inhibitive efficiency was calculated employing the equation,

$$\% \text{ Inhibition efficiency} = \frac{I - I'}{I} \times 100$$

where, I and I' are the corrosion currents without and with inhibitor, respectively.

The following inhibitors were used (dipole moment values, μ/D , in parenthesis): thiophene (0.53)¹⁴, 2-thiophenecarboxylic acid (1.96)¹⁵, 2-acetylthiophene (3.37)¹⁴ and 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde (3.55)¹⁴. The purity of these substances was checked by gas chromatography. Dipole moment characterises quantitatively the changes of the electron density in defined position caused by introduction of the given substituent to the thiophene molecule.

Results and Discussion

Anodic and cathodic Tafel plots of iron in uninhibited HNO₃ and in thiophene solutions are shown in Fig. 1. For comparison, polarisation curves measured in 2 N HNO₃ solution are also plotted. The corrosion current density for iron in 2 N HNO₃ is $i_{corr} = 13.8 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ for cathodic polarisation but it equals to 5.25 mA cm^{-2} for anodic polarisation. Addition of inhibitors induces a decrease in the i_{corr} . The slope of cathodic curves (Tafel lines) changed from 40–125 mV per current decay. The anodic polarisation curve in

2N HNO₃ has a slope of 70–125 mV. In the presence of the inhibitors, the straight line part of anodic curves is shorter than in pure acid solutions, and its slope oscillates between 25 and 60 mV per decade.

Fig. 1. Anodic and cathodic polarisation curves of iron in uninhibited 2N HNO₃ and in 2N HNO₃ containing different concentrations of 2-thiophene-carboxaldehyde: (a) 2N HNO₃ in H₂O and (b) 2N HNO₃ in alcohol, and (c) 0.5, (d) 1.0, (e) 1.5 and (f) 2.0 ml 2-thiophene-carboxaldehyde.

Fig. 2. Weight-loss vs time curves for different concentrations of 2-thiophene-carboxaldehyde; (a) 2N HNO₃ in H₂O and (b) 2N HNO₃ in alcohol, and (c) 0.5, (d) 1.0, (e) 1.5 (f) 2.0 and (g) 2.0 ml 2-thiophene-carboxaldehyde.

The results show that the inhibitors under consideration influence both the cathodic and anodic processes. The measurements of the corrosion rate reveal that the compounds are weak inhibitors. Comparison of effects of different compounds at the same concentration 0.5–2.0 ml per 100 ml medium shows that thiophene has the smallest protective ability. Substitution of one hydrogen atom in the thiophene by an electrophilic (2-COOH, 2-COCH₃, 2-CHO) group, increases the inhibitor efficiency; this increase is directly proportional to the dipole moments.

Most probably, the molecules of the inhibitor lie flat on the metal surface and the adsorption of these compounds on the metal/electrolyte phase boundary results from the interaction of π -electrons of the thiophene ring with surface metal atoms. The same mode of adsorption was assumed by Conway and Barradas¹⁰ for pyridine on mercury in 1N HCl.

The inhibition efficiency increases in the order, 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde > 2-acetylthiophene > 2-thiophenecarboxylic acid > thiophene. In strong acid solutions at pH \approx 0, one can expect that thiophene and its protonated form exist at equilibrium,

By substituting one hydrogen atom in the thiophene by a strong withdrawing group this will increase the positive charge of the cationic form and reinforce its adsorption as a result of the increased coulombic interaction¹⁰. Also these substituting groups will increase the dipole moment of the molecule. Therefore, one can expect an increase of its adsorption ability and its inhibitor efficiency as well.

The effect of thiophene derivatives on the dissolution of iron in 2N HNO₃ solution was also studied by the weight-loss method. Fig 2 repre-

Fig. 3. Percentage inhibition vs concentration curves for additives: (a) 2-thiophene-carboxaldehyde, (b) 2-acetylthiophene, (c) 2-thiophenecarboxylic acid and (d) thiophene.

sents the weight-loss vs time plots of 2-thiophene-carboxaldehyde. These plots are straight lines passing through the origin and are characterised by an initial increase in weight-loss. This linearity of the weight-loss with time from the beginning was interpreted by El-Hosary *et al.*¹⁷ as the breakdown of the oxide film and the start of the attack. Fig. 3 shows that the compounds used follow the same order when arranged according to the current efficiency at the same concentration.

The agreement of the results obtained by the two methods supports the given arrangement of the additives used in inhibiting the corrosion of iron metal in 2 N HNO₃ solution.

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